

**ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL
STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS AND
TYPE OF MANAGEMENT**

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Abstract

The important task of the educational system is to prepare students to acquire knowledge and career and cognitive skills to enter the community. Therefore, identifying the factors leading to the students' academic achievement. The socio-economic status of the parents plays a significant role in determining academic achievement of their offspring. The present study aimed to know the effect of Socio-Economic Status and type of management on their academic achievement of higher secondary school students belonging to class XI of Darjeeling. Descriptive research design survey was used. The sample consisted of 120 students of senior secondary schools in 2022-23 through random sampling. Socio-economic status scale constructed & standardized by Mishra (2022) was used in this study and Previous annual marks of the students considered as academic achievement of the students were collected from office record book. The findings of the study showed that the parents of male students have high SES than the parents of female students and government school students performed well in academic achievement in comparison to private management students. It also highlights that there is positive correlation between Socio-Economic Status & Academic Achievement and also found positive correlation between type of management of schools & academic achievement of Higher Secondary School Students.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Socio-Economic Status, Higher Secondary School students, Gender, Type of Management

INTRODUCTION:

In the present competitive world, everybody desires for a high achievement. Today's modern society expects everyone to be a high achiever. In the academic achievement school achievement may be affected by various factors like intelligence, study habits, different aspects of their personality, socio-economic status of parents, attitude of pupils towards school, the method of teaching, the quality of teachers. aptitude, interest, type of management of schools, environmental set up, number of hours spent on studies and so on. The present study aimed to investigate the relationship between socio-economic status on academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

Socio Economic Status (SES) plays a major role in the life of an adolescent. They try to make one's impact over others through high economic status, more money and high standard of living. If anything, out of these 3 things is lacking, most of them feel low in the surrounding crowd. High/low socio-economic status can either make or break an individual, especially a young individual. There have so many researches in this field which indicate that SES is the most imperative factor influencing the quality of life.

Socio economic status is considered to be an important factor to influence academic achievement of students as it is learnt from many studies that academic self-efficacy mediates relationship between socioeconomic status and academic achievement (Wiederkecher et. al (2015). It is revealed from many studies that parental level of education, occupation and annual household income are the crucial factors influencing academic achievement in the current technological and competitive society. Type of Management of Schools also plays an important role in academic achievement.

Review of Related Literature:

Related literature provides us a clear picture of the problem under research. The review of the related literature is considered essential for many reasons. It helps to identify the unanswered questions in the concerned fields on the one hand and in locating the specific issues, which require immediate and pointed attention by the Investigator. Within the minimum time, an earnest effort was made to collect the related relevant information pertaining to the area under study. some of studies are reported here-

Studies Conducted in India:

Das (2021) conducted a study on “Effect of socio-economic status on academic achievement of tribal students at secondary level in Kalahandi district” and found that significant positive correlation between socio-economic status and academic achievement of tribal students but no significant differences in the means of socio-economic status of kandha, Gond and Shabar tribal students.

Mandol (2018) examined “A study of socio-economic status and its impact to academic achievement of higher secondary school students” and found that gender does not influence academic achievement of higher secondary school students. No significant difference was found in academic achievement scores of boys’ and girls’ students having socio-economic status but significant difference was observed between high and low economic socio-economic status of boy’s students. No significant difference was found in academic achievement scores of boys’ and girls’ students having low-economic status but significant difference was observed between high and low socio-economic status of girls’ students.

Islam and Khan (2017) conducted a study on “Impact of socio-economic status on Academic achievement among the senior secondary school teachers” and found that there is a positive correlation exist between socio-economic status and academic achievement of senior secondary

school teachers, it is also high light that significant difference is present among different SES group in their academic achievement. It further revealed that there is no significant difference between male and female students in their academic achievement.

Bhat, Joshi and Wani (2016) examined “The effect of socio- economic status on academic performance of secondary school students”. The result of the study revealed that there is a significant difference in the academic achievement of high socioeconomic status of students in comparison to low socioeconomic status of students. Further examined those significant differences were found between the students with (high and low) and (high and middle) socio-economic status. On the other hand, insignificant difference was found between the students with middle and low socio-economic status in respect to academic achievement.

Amogne Asfaw Eshetu (2015) conducted a study on “Parental socio-economic status as a determinant factor of academic performance of students in regional examination” and found that there is a significant relationship between parental socio-economic conditions and academic achievements of the children in regional examination. The majority of students whose parents have better socio-economic conditions performed better as compared to those children whose parents had low socio-economic condition. Thus, it can be concluded that higher the SES higher the academic achievement.

Anwar & Ahmar (2013) conducted a study on “Socio-economic status and its relation to academic achievement of higher secondary school students” and found that gender does not influence the academic achievement of higher secondary school students. The study also revealed that males having higher socio-economic status score high academic achievement in comparison of males having low socio-economic status. There was significant difference in academic achievement of female students of high and low socio-economic students.

Studies conducted abroad:

Rifat and Bithi (2023) conducted a study on Mental Stress, Socioeconomic Status, and Academic Performance: A Critical Analysis among University Students of Bangladesh. The study sample size is 180 (n=180; male = 81 and female = 99; including case study= 05) and were collected from the students of Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University, Mymensingh, Bangladesh. The study revealed that the respondents, those with the mother's education under the SSC level (88%) have the most mental stress. Also revealed, for those whose mother's education levels are SSC/HSC (87.5%), their SES influences their academic study, and those whose mothers are undergraduate/graduate (80%) are mostly satisfied with their SES.

Vadivel et.al (2023) conducted a study on "The Impact of Low Socioeconomic background on a Child's Educational Achievements" and found that parental income has a big role to play in children's educational achievements. The results implied that economically or academically vulnerable students gain more from high behavioral involvement than their peers.

Research questions:

- Is there exist any significant difference in socio-economic status of students in relation to gender variation?
- Is there exist any significant difference in socio-economic status of students in relation to type of management variation?
- Is there exist any significant relationship between Socio-Economic Status and academic achievement?
- Is there exist any significant relationship between Type of Management of school and academic achievement?

In an attempt to give answer to these questions, the researcher has undertaken the study and stated the problem as follows.

Statement of the problem:

Dr. Samten Tamang:- ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY.....

Keeping in view of the above, the problem is stated as: “**ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS AND TYPE OF MANAGEMENT**”.

Operational definitions of the study:

Socio Economic Status: Socio economic status basically is a position of a person in relation with others based on his/her educational attainment, occupation and income etc.

Hence socio-economic status here refers to the levels of education, occupation, and income according to tool developed by the investigator Mishra-2022.

Academic Achievement: Academic Achievement is the degree and level of success and proficiency attained in the academic field.

In the present study, it refers to the scores obtained in the annual examination of class X.

Senior Secondary school students are here the students reading in class XI.

Type of Management: It refers here private and government managed schools.

Objectives of the study:

Keeping in view the need of the problem, the researcher formulated the following objectives

- I. To study the influence of socio-economic status of higher secondary school students in gender and type of management variations wise.
- II. To study the academic achievement of higher secondary school students in gender, and type of management variations wise.
- III. To study the relationship between socio-economic status & academic achievement and between type of management & academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

Hypotheses of the study:

Ho₁: There will be no significant differences in the mean scores of socio-economic status scale of the sample due to gender variation;

Ho₂: There will be no significant differences in mean scores of socio-economic status the sample due to type of management variation;

Ho₃: There will be no significant differences in the academic achievement of the sample due to gender variation.

Ho₄: There will be no significant differences in the academic achievement of the sample due to type of management variation;

Ho₅: There will be no significant correlation between socio-economic status and academic achievement of higher secondary school students;

Ho₆: There will be no significant correlation between type of management and academic achievement of higher secondary school students.

Delimitations of the Study:

- I. The study would be delimited to higher secondary school students.
- II. The study is delimited to 120 higher secondary school students out of which 60 boys & 60 girls and 60 government school students & 60 private school students studying in class XI.

Methodology:

Design: The design of the study was a descriptive study design. But the method is correlational study of ex-post facto in nature.

Population: The class XI students of higher secondary schools of Darjeeling.

Sampling Technique: Simple random sampling technique was taken for the selection of the students.

Sample: 120 students were selected from four higher secondary schools were selected.

Variables of the Study:

Independent Variable: Parental Socio-economic status and Type of Management of School.

Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement.

Categorical Variable: Gender.

THE TOOLS:

Socio-Economic Status Scale (Mishra 2022): This scale has been developed and standardized by the investigator in the three dimensions through check list (i) Education of parents (ii) occupation of parents and (iii) Income of parents.

Academic Achievement: The scores obtained in the annual examination of class X were taken.

Analysis and interpretation of data

In order to find out the results of the study mean, median, mode, standard deviation and test of significance of difference between means were calculated for all variables of Gender and Type of Management of Socio-Economic Status and academic achievement.

Summary of 't' ratio of Socio-Economic Status due to Gender and Type of management Variation

Variation	Sub samples	N	M	SD	't' Ratio	Remarks
	Boys	60	35.2759	6.35442		Significant

Gender	Girls	60	32.9032	6.52036	2.017	
Type of Management	Govt.	60	34.5091	6.1704	.708	Significant
	Private	60	33.6615	6.82660		

$t_{0.05}$ for $df\ 98 = 1.98$; $t_{0.01}$ for $df\ 98 = 2.63$

Summary of ‘t’ ratios of sub samples due to gender and type of management on Academic Achievement

Variation	Sub samples	N	M	SD	‘t’ Ratio	Remarks
Gender	Boys	60	528.5000	15.26750	2.53	Significant
	Girls	60	521.3387	15.74796		
Type of Management	Govt.	60	531.7455	16.85474	4.80	Significant
	Private	60	518.9231	12.31908		

$t_{0.05}$ for $df\ 98 = 1.98$; $t_{0.01}$ for $df\ 98 = 2.63$

On perusal of the above table, it was observed that the ‘t’ ratio in case of locale and type of family variations were significant but in case of gender, it was not significant. Boys and girls did not differ in their academic achievement. The result indicated that locale is good predictors of academic achievement. The result was in conformity with earlier studies of **Islam and Khan**

(2017). On above basis the investigator concluded that the result obtained in the present study was appropriate.

Relationship Study:

In this study also the investigator attempted to find out relationship between socio-economic status & academic achievement and between type of management of schools & academic achievement

Table

Co-efficient of co-relation between Socio-Economic Status and Academic Achievement

Academic Achievement	Socio-Economic Status		
	N	R	P
	360	.876**	.000

Interpretations:

Result of testing Ho5: on perusal of the **table 3 (i)** it was observed that the Correlation 'r' between the socio-economic status and academic achievement was found .876 and 'p' value .000 ($p < 0.001$). Hence 'r' was significant at 0.01 level of significance. Therefore, **Ho5** is rejected. So, a strong positive relationship existed between socio-economic status and academic achievement.

Findings of the study:

The findings of the study were summarized below:

- There was significant difference in socio- economic status of higher secondary school students in relation to gender variation and type of management variation

- Male students belong to higher socio-economic status than female students. On the other hand, in the type of management: Govt. students have higher socio-economic status than private school students.
- Male students performed better than female students in academic achievement. Govt. School students also showed better result than private school students.
- Positive relationship found between Socio-Economic status Academic Achievement.
- A strong and positive correlation was found between type of management and academic achievement.

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